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Universal use of face masks in COVID-19 pandemic: yes or no?

Domina Petric, MD

Because of limited supplies of surgical masks, universal face mask use in the community is probably not an option. It would be rational that self-quarantined and quarantined patients and their caregivers are supplied with respirators (FFP2, FFP3, or N95). All vulnerable individuals (elderly, immunocompromised) should wear a respirator, or at least surgical mask if available. It is crucial to supply all healthcare professionals that are in contact with infected patients with respirators and all other medical staff with surgical masks.

WHO currently recommends that people should wear face masks if they have **respiratory symptoms** or if they are caring for someone presenting with these symptoms. Feng and coworkers recommended that it would also be rational that people in quarantine wear face masks if they need to leave home for any reason, to prevent potential asymptomatic or pre-symptomatic transmission. Vulnerable populations, such as older adults and those with underlying medical conditions, should wear face masks if available. Universal use of face masks could be considered if supplies permit, but important reason to discourage widespread use of face masks is to **preserve limited supplies** for professional use in health-care settings. Universal face mask use in the community has also been discouraged with the argument that face masks provide no

effective protection against coronavirus infection¹.

A surgical mask protects against infectious agents transmitted by droplets of saliva or secretions from the upper respiratory tract. It does not protect against airborne infectious agents such as coronavirus.

A respirator is personal protective equipment (not available in pharmacy) that prevents the wearer from inhaling aerosols (dust, smoke, and mist) as well as vapors or gases (disinfectants, anesthetic gases). It protects the wearer from airborne infectious agents such as coronavirus.

In Europe, for caregivers, it is necessary to wear a respirator of at least class FFP2 or FFP3 for maximum filtration of particles and aerosols when caring for a patient who is suspected of being so².

In the United States, the N95 respirator filters 95% of airborne particles, and can even filter out bacteria and viruses, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. So for caregivers, it is necessary to wear a respirator of class N, R or P³.

Because of limited supplies of surgical masks, universal face mask use in the community is probably not an option.

It would be rational that patients who are in self-isolation (and in quarantine) are supplied with respirators (FFP2, FFP3 or N95) by their epidemiologist or other medical provider, so they can wear the respirator if they need to leave home for any reason. It would be also rational that caregivers (family members and other caregivers of self-isolated patients) are supplied with respirators so they can be protected when in contact with a self-isolated patient.

It is crucial to supply all healthcare professionals that are in contact with infected patients with respirators and all other medical staff with surgical masks.

It would be rational to provide to all at-risk individuals (elderly, immunocompromised) at least surgical masks, possibly respirators, so they can be protected if they must leave their homes for any reason.

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